

FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF HEMP FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Fatigue lifetime studies of hemp fibre reinforced polyester have shown that pre-alkalisation of the fibres can improve performance, that immersion in water has little effect and that impact damage tolerance is poor. Additionally, minimal stiffness degradation and damage accumulation during fatigue provided no warning of the final brittle failure.

Keywords: hemp; fatigue; impact; alkalisation; distilled water, stiffness degradation.

INTRODUCTION

The use of natural fibres as a replacement for traditional glass fibres in composites has gained increasing importance in recent years as environmental concerns have led to a quest for sustainable alternatives. Natural fibre composites have generally been found to have limitations in their mechanical properties, particularly with regard to impact resistance. They also present various other challenges that with glass fibres may have already been addressed, such as fibre surface treatment to optimise interfacial bonding and sensitivity to water.

Like other mechanical properties, the fatigue behaviour of natural fibre composites is still not fully understood. Studies into both thermoplastic and thermoset based natural fibre composites have been carried out by Gassan [1]. Their composites, made with flax and jute fibre yarns in epoxy, polyester and polypropylene matrices, were tested in tension-tension fatigue ($R=0.1$ and 10 Hz frequency). They investigated the influence of type of fibre, textile architecture, fibre-matrix adhesion, fibre mechanical properties and amount of fibre on tension-tension fatigue behaviour. Due to differences in fibre fine structure and surface morphology, significant differences in composite damping were measured between unidirectional flax and jute-epoxy composites, with an approximately two-fold increase in damping for the flax-epoxy composites. Damage propagation was quite similar for both types of composites.

The influence of textile architecture was investigated using unidirectional and woven reinforced jute-epoxy composites. Critical load for damage initiation and load at failure

was lower and damage propagation was more rapid for the composites based on woven reinforcements.

The quality of fibre–matrix adhesion was shown to have a significant effect on the fatigue behaviour of both reinforced brittle polyesters and ductile polypropylene matrices. For both, the critical load for damage initiation was lower and damage propagation was more rapid for composites with untreated woven jute.

Fibre strength and modulus were found to influence the critical load for damage initiation, the rate of damage propagation and the load at failure in unidirectional flax–epoxy composites. Increasing fibre mechanical properties increased the critical load and the failure load, while damage propagation was reduced. Composite damping was reduced with increasing fibre fraction below and above the critical load for damage initiation, with comparable rates for damage propagation.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Plaques were made using two layers of non-woven randomly oriented hemp fibre mat hand laid up in a conventional unsaturated polyester matrix and subjected to relatively high moulding pressure, giving fibre weight fractions of just over 50%. End-tabbed parallel-sided samples (125mm by 20mm by 2.5mm thick) were cut from the plaques and the edges polished to reduce stress concentrating defects. Fatigue testing was carried out in tension-tension mode ($R = 0.1$) at a frequency of 1Hz. The fatigue testing was carried out as per BS ISO 13003:2003 (Fibre-reinforced plastics – Determination of fatigue properties under cyclic loading conditions). Some plaques were made from alkalinized fibres to evaluate the effect of fibre surface treatments on the fatigue properties of composites. Fibres were soaked in 1%, 5% or 10% sodium hydroxide solutions for 24 hours. Fibres were then washed and dried before making plaques in the same way. Environmental fatigue tests were carried out with the samples immersed in distilled water in a specially designed Perspex water chamber during the testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The $S-N$ curve of hemp/polyester composites with an average fibre weight fraction of 52% is shown in Fig. 1. The dashed lines in the figure represent the 95% confidence limit of the linear regression line. The variability of properties of hemp fibres is expected to result in random accumulation of damage in the composites and, therefore, it is not surprising to see scatter in the data points with some lying outside the 95% confidence limit. It has also been reported for glass fibre composites that the normal scatter in static strength data is often increased by random damage during fatigue loading [2].

The best-fit regression line in Fig. 1 shows gradual decline in fatigue strength with increase in the number of fatigue cycles. The regression line predicts an endurance limit of about 20 MPa for the composite at 1 million cycles which corresponded well with the experimental data as shown by arrowheads. Hence a stress level of up to about 20 MPa (approximately 40% of UTS) can be taken as a safe value for endurance limit for this composite.

Fig. 1: S-N curve of hemp fibre composites

In order to compare the fatigue sensitivity of these composites with other materials, it is more suitable to use the normalised stress versus cycles to failure curve. The normalised stress (maximum fatigue tensile stress divided by ultimate static tensile strength) versus cycles to failure curve is shown in Fig. 2. The curve shows that the fatigue strength of the composite was reduced from the static strength by almost 10% per decade of cycles. A similar value of reduction in static strength was reported by Mandell [3] for unidirectional E-glass fibre reinforced composites in the fibre direction. Thus these randomly oriented hemp fibre composites are observed to show similar fatigue sensitivity to unidirectional glass fibre composites.

The normalised S-N curve is represented by the equation,

$$\sigma_a / \sigma_{uts} = 1 - b \log N$$

where σ_a is the applied peak stress, σ_{uts} is the static strength, and the constant b , which represents the slope of the normalised S-N curve, is called fatigue sensitivity coefficient. The value of b was found to be 0.097 for this hemp fibre composite. Mandell [3] collected S-N data (from 64 S-N data sets available in literature) for tension-tension fatigue for various chopped E-glass strand composites (both SMC and CSM) and found that the value

of b for all the systems was remarkably equal or close to 0.1. This value of b was the same for unidirectional continuous glass fibre composites fatigue tested parallel to the fibres. A similar value of b for this hemp fibre composite seems to reinforce the fact that it has comparable fatigue sensitivity to that of glass fibre composites.

Fig. 2: Normalised $S-N$ curve of hemp fibre composites

Most composites fail in fatigue in a similar mode and by the same mechanisms as under static loading. Such behaviour was observed for hemp fibre composites. In both static tensile testing and tensile fatigue loading, the samples failed in a completely brittle and catastrophic manner, normal to the direction of applied stress, and no crack or damage was seen to form on the surface before eventual failure. The brittle nature of the fracture of a typical sample cracked in fatigue testing is shown Fig. 3.

The fatigue fractured sample has a similar appearance to that fractured in tensile testing. Therefore it can be expected that damage development modes in fatigue were quite similar to those in tensile testing. This is also borne out by the SEM micrograph of the fracture surface as shown in Fig. 4. It is clear from the image that the principal modes of failure in tension-tension fatigue are matrix fracture, fibre fracture, fibre/matrix debonding, and fibre pull-out. Similar modes of failure were also observed in fracture surfaces of samples in tensile testing.

Fig. 3: Fracture of a hemp fibre composite sample in fatigue testing

Fig. 4: SEM micrograph of fracture surfaces of samples in fatigue testing

Fatigue properties following low-velocity impact:

The relatively poor low velocity impact properties of hemp fibre composites that have been reported could also lead to degradation of their post-impact fatigue properties. It is therefore important to study the effect of low-velocity impact on their fatigue properties.

Fig. 5: Comparison of *S-N* curves of impacted and non-impacted composites

Samples of hemp fibre reinforced polyester composites that had been subjected to low velocity impact of energy levels of 1, 2, and 3J were subsequently fatigue tested in tension-tension mode at a frequency of 1 Hz ($R=0.1$). The resulting *S-N* curves (Fig. 5) showed significant deterioration in fatigue performance as a result of the impact. However, when the data were normalized against the post impact tensile strength (Fig. 6), then, despite the large scatter in data, these normalized *S-N* curves all had similar gradients. This suggests that the effect of damage on fatigue performance was similar to the effect on static tensile strength. The values of the fatigue sensitivity coefficients of impacted samples were found to be quite similar, suggesting that after the residual tensile strength is taken into account, the effect of impact damage on fatigue strength is the same, regardless of the impact energy level. It might be noted that the gradients are, if anything slightly lower for damaged samples than for undamaged material, suggesting lower fatigue sensitivity, but the large scatter in the data make this equivocal.

Fatigue properties of alkalisied fibre composites:

Hemp fibres were pre-treated in various concentrations of NaOH to study the effect of such surface alikalisiation on the composite fatigue properties. The comparison of *S-N* curves (Fig. 7) show a measurable improvement in fatigue performance of composites made with fibres from 1% and 5% solutions. However following fibre treatment at the higher NaOH concentration of 10%, fatigue performance was reduced to about the same level as

composites with untreated fibres. This points at the positive effect of fibre surface treatment, possibly resulting in improved fibre/matrix adhesion, on the fatigue properties of these composites.

Fig. 6: Comparison of normalised $S-N$ curves of impacted and non-impacted composites

Fatigue properties of composites immersed in water:

Hemp fibres contain water and their moisture content varies with ambient conditions and so the sensitivity to water of their composites needs careful evaluation. In this study some composite samples were pre-immersed in distilled water until they were saturated, prior to fatigue testing in water (pre-conditioned), and others were fatigue tested in distilled water without pre-immersion (non-conditioned). The comparison of $S-N$ (Fig. 8) showed that neither pre-immersion nor testing in water had any significant effect on the fatigue lifetime data. The fatigue sensitivity coefficients in water were similar to those for dry composites. This seems to suggest that the fatigue strength of these composites is not affected by immersion in water.

Fig. 7: Comparison of *S-N* curves of alkalisied fibre composites

Fig. 8: Comparison of *S-N* curves of composites immersed in water

Stiffness degradation during fatigue:

During the fatigue testing, some samples were periodically removed from the fatigue machine so that their residual stiffness could be monitored. Results (Fig. 9) showed that these hemp based composites suffered little stiffness degradation with increasing fatigue cycles until they failed suddenly in a brittle fashion. This behaviour is unlike that of glass fibre polyester composites with a $\pm 45^\circ$ layup, which undergo gradual stiffness degradation as fatigue progresses [4]. This lack of stiffness degradation as fatigue progresses is similar to the behaviour seen in glass fibre composites with chopped strand mat and $0/90^\circ$ geometries and so it would seem that it is more a result of the fibre geometry than the fibre type. Composites with some fibres along the test direction (such as $0/90^\circ$ or random mat geometries) tend to fail catastrophically with little warning of damage progression.

Fig. 9: Stiffness degradation of hemp fibre composites at different stress levels

Fatigue in tension-compression loading:

Tension-compression fatigue loading was carried out at $R = -1$ and frequency of 1 Hz. In order to prevent the buckling of the samples during loading, a specially designed anti-buckling device was clamped on to the samples throughout the testing. The $S-N$ curve (Fig. 10) showed that fatigue resistance in tension-compression was considerably lower than that in tension-tension fatigue. The fatigue sensitivity coefficient is also much lower in tension-

compression loading at 0.122 as against 0.097 in tension-tension loading. In this respect, hemp fibre composites behave similar to synthetic fibre composites.

Fig. 10: S-N curves of hemp fibre composites in tension-compression fatigue loading

CONCLUSIONS

1. Hemp fibre polyester composites have similar fatigue sensitivity to glass fibre composites.
2. Tensile strength and fatigue strength are degraded following low velocity impact; however when the residual tensile strength is taken into account, the effect of impact damage on fatigue resistance is similar regardless of impact energy level.
3. Pre-alkalisation of fibres produces composites with measurable improvement in their fatigue resistance, the result being more pronounced for 1% and 5% alkalisated fibre composites than 10% alkalisated fibre composites.
4. These composites showed no deterioration in fatigue resistance in water.
5. These composites showed little degradation of stiffness or evidence of damage during fatigue loading prior to sudden brittle failure.
6. The degradation in fatigue resistance is greater in tension-compression than that in tension-tension.

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